

Adoption of Local Technology and Materials for Sustainable Green Buildings in Southwest Nigeria

^{*1}Ikudayisi Ayodele Emmanuel and ²Afolami Adewale James

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ABSTRACT

Adopting local building technology and materials for sustainable green buildings in Nigeria is a critical endeavour that aligns with the sustainable development goals (SDGs 11) which addresses sustainable cities development. The study investigates impact of local technology and materials (LTM) in the building construction practices in Southwest, Nigeria. A purposive sampling survey method was adopted using questionnaires from 100 professionals in the construction experts. Descriptive and inferential statistics were employed for mean ranking and Kruskal-Wallis (H-test) estimates for comparison of perspectives on LTM. The results show that job creation ($M=4.08$) and improved domestic economy ($M=4.06$) are the main economic and social benefits of LTM. Although, challenges such as lack of skilled labour, resistance to adoption, and limited awareness are apparent, yet, many of the experts showed willingness to adopt LTM in future projects. Based on mean rankings, strategies for promoting use of LTM are training programs for architects, engineers, and construction workers ($M=4.05$), local communities' participation ($M=4.02$), and scaling technology and materials ($M=4.01$). The study recommends inclusive training programs for architects, engineers, and construction workers on the use of LTMs for sustainable buildings. Creating enabling environment for adopting LTM requires a deeper integration of industry professionals for better acceptability.

Keywords: Construction, Built Environment, Bio-based Materials, Green Building, Sustainability

^{1,2}Department of Architecture, Federal University of Technology Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria

*Corresponding author email: aeikudayisi@futa.edu.ng

INTRODUCTION

The construction industry consumes the most natural resources on the planet and is responsible for 30% of the world's solid waste production, 40% of its raw material consumption, and 40% of its CO₂ emissions (Chanchangi et al., 2023). Thus, construction industries are expected to reduce resource consumption and become more environmentally friendly due to the rising climate warming. Globally, the construction sectors are currently placing a high priority on green buildings, an environmental sustainability strategy that focuses on adoption of local material and technology (LTM) towards achieving energy

efficient, less-pollutants with a healthier environment for occupants (Agyekum, 2019; Ikudayisi & Adegun, 2025).

The World Green Building Council defines green building as ‘a building that, in its design, construction or operation, reduces or eliminates negative impacts, and can create positive impacts, on our climate and natural environment (World Green Building Council, 2014). Taking account of various aspects of sustainability, including environmental, economic, and social considerations, green buildings preserve natural resources and improve quality of life. This drive addresses the challenges posed by rapid urbanization and the built environment's contribution to climate change (Jegede & Taki, 2022). The green building movement advocates for the reuse of pre-existing structures, reduction in construction waste, recycled building materials, and improvement in post occupancy comfort and health of built environments.

Green building is distinguished from traditional construction approaches by a number of fundamental ideas and practices which includes resource efficiency (Alohan & Oyetunji, 2021), energy efficiency (Amaripadath & Sailor, 2024), healthy indoor environmental quality (Nunayon & Zhong, 2025), the use of sustainable materials (Oke, et al. 2024) among others. The transition to sustainable materials is important to mitigate climate change and this will also be taken care off at design (Yousef & Elmansoury, 2021) and operations (Mitkees et al. 2023) phase. According to Asdrubali et al. (2015), the thermal occupant centric and acoustic insulating material using natural or recycled material in buildings improves the quality of life. The potentials of material to be classified as green and sustainable building materials according to Kim and Rigdon (1998) should include embodied energy reduction means, use of naturally occurring materials, energy efficiency, use of non-toxic or less-toxic materials, renewable energy systems. In addition, the materials will have higher durability, re-usability, recyclability, and biodegradability components (Bredenoord, 2017).

Leveraging local technology and materials (LTM) for sustainable green buildings aligns with eco-friendly policy actions for harnessing diversity of local contexts and traditional practices. This initiative can create buildings that are not only environmentally responsible but also culturally and economically beneficial. The use of LTMs in construction projects is challenged by some factors embedded in perception of quality (Mahmoud & Zaheer. (2020); Agyekum, et al. (2021), affordability (Ugochukwu & Chioma, 2015); acceptability and material selection (Akadiri, 2015; Alohan & Oyetunji 2021). Studies on local materials in sustainable building projects includes compressed earth blocks as alternative for housing in villages of Upper Egypt (Hanafi, 2021; Neyya et al. 2025); bamboo (Bredenoord, 2017) and roof truss systems found in low- and medium-income house designs in South Africa (Crafford et al. 2017). Earthen construction materials were found to be cheaper, cleaner with greater thermal comfort and addressed as solution to sustainable buildings (Adegun & Adedeji, 2017).

Jegede and Taki (2022) evaluated optimization of building envelopes using indigenous materials to achieve thermal comfort and affordable housing in Abuja, Nigeria. The use of silicon-based paint was found to improve the strength and water resistance of the stabilized clay bricks (El Mahllawy et al, 2018). The feasibility of stabilizing clay bricks with marble cutting waste (MCW) demonstrated optimum content at 15% as replacement for hydrated lime in the production of stabilized clay brick. The use of local waste materials as a substitute for a hydrated lime binder reduces both the cost and environmental impact associated with block production. Ayeni et al (2021) examined the use kaolin clay as an environmentally friendly option in building construction in Katsina. The Kankara metakaolin-based geopolymers serve as a potential sustainable construction material for the Nigerian construction industry due to its availability, affordability, compressive strength values, and eco-friendliness.

Boulebbina et al, (2022) study on passive solar house prototype with a bio-based material show that the experimental and numerical simulation results are in good agreement. The optimal orientation of bio-based materials has proven its effectiveness in the construction of the passive solar house. Osuizugbo et al. (2024) examined the technology-related factors of zero-carbon buildings (ZCBs) in Lagos and found its benefit to human and biodiversity impeded by poor acceptability and cost of maintenance. In their thermal comfort assessment of compressed earthen based buildings, Neya et al. (2025) found a better valorization of clay potential in the use of geopolymer binder as a suitable ecological option for the replacement of the cement binder.

Nigeria's construction industry relies heavily on conventional construction materials, leading to high carbon footprint. The country is experiencing rapid urbanization and population growth, leading to increased demand for housing and infrastructure (Nwokediegwu et al., 2024). Yet, this growth also presents significant challenges related to environmental sustainability, resource scarcity, and climate change. Many existing local and waste materials are greatly overlooked and underutilized (Ikudayisi & Odeyale, 2021). Despite the growing interest of the region about the importance of decarbonizing the construction industry, limited attention has been given to the role of local materials and wastes (Agyekum, 2019).

The concept of leveraging local building technology and materials for green buildings in Nigeria is based on the idea that traditional building methods and materials are often well-suited for creating sustainable buildings. For example, many traditional African building materials, such as mudbrick and bamboo, are naturally energy-efficient and have a low environmental impact. Additionally, traditional building methods often incorporate features such as natural ventilation and passive solar heating, which can help to reduce the energy consumption of building (Chanchangi et al., 2023; Ikudayisi & Odeyale, 2021; Nwokediegwu et al.2024). In Nigeria, studies have shown that date palm trees from agricultural residues, combination of bone and palm bunch ash for lateritic soil stabilization (Ifeyinwa et al. 2021) and recycled plastic bottles

(RPB) are some of the sustainable materials used for sustainable housing projects in Nigeria (Solaja et al., 2020).

Extant studies have shown that LTMs have been used for sustainable buildings. However, it is imperative to understand the level of benefits of adoption in areas of economic, social impact of utilizing local building technology and materials in sustainable green building projects. The study fills the gap as it assesses the growth strategies of utilization and scaling LTM in green buildings within the professionals working in the construction industry.

The aim of this research is to investigate issues on adoption of LTM in Nigeria with the view of identifying promotion strategies. Specifically, the study analyzes the economic, technological and social impact of utilizing local building technology and materials in sustainable green building projects, identify the constraints and challenges and assess how local technology and materials can be promoted and the willingness to its adoption.

METHODOLOGY

A quantitative method was employed with the goal of offering a comprehensive understanding of the indigenous building technology materials used in Nigeria. Southwest Nigeria was the focal point for the study due to its importance in construction and urban development. A purposive sampling was employed in the selection of respondents through their professional association's platforms in two states namely Ondo and Oyo. Key participants include architects, engineers, builders, contractors, and project managers, producers and distributors of construction supplies.

A structured questionnaire survey for data collection was distributed using Google Forms, an adaptable and user-friendly online data gathering tool. The Google Forms facilitated distribution of the questionnaire to the selected participants in a timely manner. The questionnaire covers thematic areas related to the research objectives such advantages and effects of using local building materials, the current barriers and challenges in adoption, and the willingness to use local building technology. From the responses retrieved, only 100 responses were found useful for the analysis. The Statistical Packages for Social Scientist (SPSS 23) was used for the descriptive and inferential analysis.

The Kruskal-Wallis H test was employed for the correlations and differences between variables to compare the responses of professionals from different sectors within the construction industry, such as architects, engineers, builders, contractors, and project managers. When the presumptions for parametric tests, such as the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), are not met, one non-parametric technique called the Kruskal-Wallis test is used to compare the medians of two or more groups. It evaluates whether there are statistically significant differences between groups based on a single ordinal or continuous dependent variable measured on an ordinal or continuous scale. The test ascertains whether there are significant variations in perceptions

or attitudes towards local building technology materials among these diverse groups. This analysis provides valuable insights into the nuances and disparities within the industry, aiding in the formulation of targeted strategies and interventions for promoting the adoption of sustainable building practices in Nigeria.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profiling the research population presents a road map for better understanding of participant’s professional characteristics. The result of educational background (Table 1) shows that majority were literate with degree holder above HND level. In the professional cadre, engineers had greater representation forming 36% of the respondents while 26% were architects. Over three quarter of the respondents are within the first five years of their professional experience and followed by 6-10 years. The background information further deepens the understanding of the participant’s knowledge in construction practices and provide relevant insights essential in the use of LTM. This finding corroborates the work of Oke et al. (2024) who found that professional knowledge is important in the integration of sustainable materials in construction practice of Nigerian quantity surveying firms.

Table 1: Professional’s Characteristics

Variables	Categories	Relative Distribution
Educational Background	No formal education	3(3%)
	Primary school	1(1%)
	ND/NCE	8(8%)
	HND/Degree	54(54%)
	Postgraduate	24(24%)
Role in the construction industry	Architect	26(26%)
	Builder	12(12%)
	Client	1(1%)
	Contractor	13(13%)
	Electrical	1(13%)
	Engineer	36(36%)
	Others	11(11%)
Years of experience	0-5	3
	6-10	79
	11-20	17
	>20	1

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey, 2024.

Economic, Technological, and Social Impacts/Benefits of Use of Local Building Technology

The benefit derived in terms of the economic, technological, and social impacts of utilizing local building technology is presented in Table 2. The first five ranked factors of major impact and benefit of utilizing local building technology and materials include job creation, improved local economy, traditional conservation, indigenous community power and low imported materials. Use of local technology signals a pathway for job creation as demand for materials increases. The local production alongside wide acceptability contributes significantly to the local economy with a mean value of 4.06. Leveraging indigenous knowledge for sustainable green building preserves traditional building practices and enhances its application for inclusive and sustainable economic development. In their study, Agwu et al. (2025) found utilization of LTM has positive impacts with respect to job creation opportunities, traditional knowledge integration through local content creations.

Table 2: Economic, Technological, and Social Impacts/Benefits of Utilizing Local Building Technology

S/ N	Impacts/Benefits	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Rank
1	Lower cost	3.68	100	1.024	9
2	Sustainability	3.52	100	1.123	12
3	Job creation	4.08	100	1.012	1
4	Aesthetics	3.30	100	1.096	15
5	Identity creation	3.83	100	1.025	7
6	Innovation and new building techniques	3.63	100	1.125	11
7	Comfortability	3.41	100	1.164	14
8	Low imported materials	3.92	100	0.992	5
9	Indigenous community power	4.00	100	0.910	4
10	Higher quality	3.43	100	1.121	13
11	Low environmental impact	3.66	100	1.007	10
12	Social inclusiveness	3.76	100	1.026	8
13	Traditional conservation	4.03	100	0.958	3
14	Sustainable economic development	3.84	100	0.950	6
15	Improved local economy	4.06	100	0.886	2

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2024.

Comparison on Economic, Technological, and Social Impacts/Benefits of Utilizing Local Building Technology

The result of the Kruskal-Wallis H Test estimates on comparison of the responses of various professionals in the construction industry to benefits of use of local building technology is presented in Table 3. The Kruskal-Wallis H Test asymptotic p-value shows the level of significance at 0.05. If the p-value is larger, the null hypothesis is accepted, otherwise it is rejected. Lower cost was the only significant estimate with no statistically significant difference in the responses of the various professionals. It shows all the professionals agreed to lower cost as key benefits to use of local technology and material in Nigeria. This finding was supported by the study of Adegun and Adedeji (2017) who reported advancing earthen based materials with lower construction cost and costs to the environment as solutions to housing issues. Cost savings from use of local technology and materials in construction process were found significant by Agwu et al. (2025), thereby making sustainable housing affordable.

Table 3: The Kruskal-Wallis H Test ranking table for economic, technological, and social impacts/benefits of utilizing local building technology

S/N	Rank Variables	Architect	Builder	Engineer	Contractor	Others	Kruskal-Wallis H	Asymp. Sig.
		Mean Rank						
		26	12	36	13	13		
1	Lower cost	59.88	40.71	52.07	45.85	41.08	12.942	0.012
2	Sustainable buildings	51.92	44.53	54.60	48.69	43.81	3.420	0.490
3	Job creation	56.77	43.88	51.61	49.08	42.42	5.420	0.247
4	Aesthetic	46.77	51.38	49.04	59.92	51.77	0.252	0.993
5	Identity creation	47.17	46.75	49.69	56.23	57.12	0.807	0.938
6	Innovation and new building techniques	57.58	38.92	49.94	48.81	50.27	1.921	0.750
7	Comfortability	58.00	39.25	54.01	45.77	40.88	1.290	0.863
8	Low imported materials	52.08	51.25	52.39	52.50	39.42	5.872	5.872
9	Indigenous community power	41.17	49.17	51.85	46.62	51.48	4.566	4.556

10	Higher quality	50.83	50.35	50.42	48.73	57.44	1.838	1.838
11	Low environmental impact	46.04	51.33	51.81	37.12	53.13	5.112	5.112
12	Social inclusiveness	47.63	54.18	43.69	44.50	54.52	7.064	7.064
13	Traditional conservation	43.38	46.86	55.96	53.65	50.77	4.888	4.888
14	Sustainable economic development	61.08	48.08	49.08	48.31	48.79	3.942	3.942
15	Improved local economy	48.42	50.42	50.12	56.46	39.42	1.921	0.750

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2024.

Constraints and Challenges Associated with Local Technology and Materials

The categorization of the constraints and challenges associate with local building technology and materials utilization using the mean rank is presented in Table 4. The most significant constraint and challenge associated with local technology and materials is the lack of skilled labor in the use of LTM. The variable ranked first among the other variables with the highest mean value of 3.84 (S.D= 1.188) followed by mean value of lack of community support for the use of LTM (S.D = 1.097). Resistance to adopting LTM by consumers due to perceived materials came third with a mean value of 3.82. Skill manpower, enabling environment and acceptability/affordability of local technology and materials are major constraints to utilization of LTM.

This was buttressed by the findings of Ikudayisi and Adegun (2025) as low level of competency, and dearth of technological enablers inhibit the growth of green building projects. Hamza et al. (2019) emphasized integrating green skills in building construction programs as a pathway to achieving environmental sustainability in green buildings. Lack of expertise was part of the factors identified by Agyekum et al., (2021) as limitations to the adoption of hemp as an alternative sustainable material for green building delivery in Ghana. According to Osuizugbo et al. (2024) inadequate technical expertise required in technological advancements, poor translation of research outcomes innovations, and construction industry's resistance to local technologies are obstacles to utilization of LTM in Lagos, Nigeria.

Table 4: Constraints and Challenges Associated with Local Technology and Materials (LTM)

S/N	Constraints and Challenges	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Rank
1	Lack of awareness and understanding	3.00	100	1.114	15
2	Lack of training and education on the use	3.39	100	1.004	11
3	Lack of government incentives and support	3.17	100	1.002	14
4	Local building materials may not meet modern building standards	3.21	100	1.123	13
5	Local building techniques may not be suitable for modern construction	3.65	100	1.072	7
6	Lack of standardization and quality control for LTM	3.46	100	0.972	10
7	Lack of access to financing for the use of local building technology	3.36	100	1.055	12
8	The use of local building materials may have environmental impacts	3.68	100	1.131	5
9	Lack of sustainable sourcing and harvest practices for LTM	3.75	100	0.932	4
10	The cost of transportation of local building materials may be high	3.67	100	1.295	6
11	Cultural preferences and tradition may favor the use of imported materials	3.61	100	1.155	8
12	Lack of community support for the use of LTM	3.84	100	1.097	2
13	Consumers may be resistant to adopting LTM due to performance	3.82	100	0.989	3
14	Lack of skilled labor in the use of LTM	3.84	100	1.188	1
15	Lack of waste management and recycling practices	3.60	100	1.067	9

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2024.

Strategies to Promote Local Building Technologies and Materials in Nigeria

The mean rank analysis for the strategies to promote local building technologies and materials in the Southwest Nigeria is presented in Table 5. Training was the most significant strategies to promote local building technologies and materials in Nigeria. Most ranked is training programs for core professionals like architects, engineers, and construction workers on the use of local building technology and materials. Bredenoord (2017) supported the findings as the study identified targeted training and policy reforms as essential growth factors in technology development of LTM for a sustainable built environment. Also, local

communities training came second with mean value 4.02 and demonstration of projects that showcase the potential of LTM (4.01). Fostering policies for local content use of technology and materials and integration into building codes will sustain utilization. Hatipoğlu and Yakın (2025) reiterated the impact of nano materials in design process and the demonstration of their potential to achieve sustainability goals in areas of thermal efficiency, durability, and environmental footprint.

Table 5: Strategies to Promote Local Building Technologies and Materials (LTM) in Nigeria

S/ N	Strategies	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Rank
1	Incorporation of local building technology and materials into school curricula	3.75	100	1.048	11
2	The government should provide financial support for local producers of LTM	4.00	100	1.015	4
3	Public awareness campaigns to educate the public about the benefits of LTM	3.95	100	0.925	7
4	Demonstration projects that showcase the potential of LTM	4.01	100	0.937	3
5	Media coverage that highlights the benefits of LTM	3.92	100	0.981	10
6	Local communities should be trained in the use of LTM	4.02	100	0.932	2
7	Local communities should be empowered to monitor and enforce building codes and standards related to the use of LTM	3.94	100	0.962	9
8	Local communities should be involved in the planning and implementation of public projects that utilize LTM	3.95	100	0.947	8
9	The government should promote the use of LTM in public procurements	3.99	100	0.882	5
10	The government should establish standards and quality control mechanisms for LTM	3.97	100	1.010	6
11	Training programs for architects, engineers, and construction workers on the use of LTM	4.05	100	0.947	1
12	The government should provide tax incentives for the use of LTM	3.74	100	1.060	12
13	The government should implement policies that mandate the use of LTM in public projects.	3.65	100	1.067	13

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2024.

Willingness to Adopt Local Building Technology and Materials

The analysis for willingness to adopt local building technology and materials is presented in Table 6. Result shows that 48% of the respondents are willing to adopt local building technology and materials whereas 6% of the respondents are unwilling and 6% are highly unwilling. Therefore, this signifies that majority of the respondents are willing to adopt local building technology and materials. Risk aversion in adoption of new technologies and uncertainty of wide range of new products acceptability is critical in local technology and materials (Agyekum et al. 2021) due to global environmental threats. Also, willingness of early adopters might not translate to a more reactive mass production and market. Creation of awareness within the construction industry will foster use of local technology and materials in sustainable green buildings in Nigeria.

Table 6: Willingness to Adopt Local Building Technology and Materials (LTM)

	Frequency	Percentage
Highly Unwilling	6	6.0
Unwilling	6	6.0
Neutral	17	17.0
Willing	48	48.0
Highly willing	23	23.0
	100	100.0

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey, 2024.

Comparison on Willingness to Adopt Local Building Technology and Materials

The result of the Kruskal-Wallis H Test on willingness to adopt local building technology and materials technologies and materials in Nigeria, which compares the responses of various professionals in the construction industry is presented in Table 7. The Kruskal-Wallis H Test p value is at the significance level of 0.05. The p value from the test statistics variables is 0.513. The Kruskal-Wallis H Test shows that there is no statistically significant difference in the responses of the various professionals for willingness of adoption of local technology and material.

Table 7: The Kruskal-Wallis H Test estimates for willingness to adopt LTM

Rank Variables	Profession	N	Mean Rank
Willingness to Adopt Local Building Technology and Materials	Architect	26	57.50
	Builder	12	42.50
	Engineer	36	48.69
	Contractor	13	46.73
	Others	13	52.65
	Total	100	
	Asymp. Sig.	0.513	

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey, 2024

CONCLUSION

This study empirically investigates the adoption of local technology and materials in the construction industry towards sustainable green building in the Southwest Nigeria. Analysis was done using descriptive and inferential statistics particularly the mean ranking and Kruskal-Wallis H for comparison of responses. The findings identify important factors for effective promotion of local building technology. Professional view on the economic, technological and social benefits shows that utilizing local building technology enhances creation of job opportunities, boost domestic economy, and scaling of indigenous conservation practices. The Kruskal-Wallis H estimates on comparison of professional’s responses on benefits derived show lower cost as the only significant variable and a key benefit to use of local technology and material in Nigeria.

Findings revealed dearth of skilled labor, lack of community support for the use, and resistance to adoption of LTM by consumers as major constraints and challenge associated with local technology and materials. Furthermore, greater proportions of construction experts are willing to adopt local technology and use of materials in their construction practices. Mean ranking estimates reveals the significant strategies to promote local building technologies and materials in southwest Nigeria. These include training programs for architects, engineers, and construction workers and inclusion of local communities’ participation in the use of local building technology and materials. Also, demonstration of projects that showcase the potential of technology and use of material provide a benchmark for better integration in green building construction processes.

The scope of the study is limited to southwest region only. It could be beneficial if the scope is extended to the other geopolitical zone of Nigeria for comprehensive assessment of use of LTM. This is an area for future research. However, the study presented a holistic view on factors needed for adoption and overall significant impact on use of local technology and materials even with substantial mean rankings observed.

The study brought to fore significant gains spanning economic, social, and environmental in the use and support of technologies in integration of sustainable green building in Nigeria.

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